

EBFMC25-IP-12 · Lung Cancer Screening Strategies: Risk Factors, Early Diagnosis, and Future Perspective

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15831999>

This invited paper was presented as a keynote speech at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is included in the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Selen Karaoglanoglu

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9274-6237>

AFFILIATIONS

Ordu University Faculty of Medicine

Department of Pulmonology

Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Background: Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer-related deaths both worldwide and in Türkiye. A major challenge is the late-stage diagnosis in the majority of cases, significantly lowering survival rates.

Objective: This presentation aims to emphasize the significance of early detection in lung cancer, discuss current global screening strategies—particularly low-dose computed tomography (LDCT)—and reflect on Türkiye's current situation and needs.

Summary: According to 2020 data, 59% of lung cancer patients in Türkiye were diagnosed at stage 4. Studies like the National Lung Screening Trial (NLST) have demonstrated that LDCT screening reduces lung cancer mortality by 20% in high-risk populations. Despite international progress, Türkiye lacks a national screening program. Early diagnosis not only increases survival but also improves quality of life and reduces economic burden.

Conclusion: Family physicians have a key role in identifying high-risk individuals and referring them appropriately. There is a need to establish cost-effective, evidence-based screening strategies tailored to Türkiye's healthcare system to enable earlier detection and better outcomes in lung cancer.

KEYWORDS

Lung cancer, early diagnosis, LDCT screening, lung cancer screening

INTRODUCTION

Lung cancer is one of the most commonly diagnosed cancers both in our country and globally, and it remains the leading cause of cancer-related deaths (GLOBOCAN, 2022). According to data from the Public Health General Directorate of the Republic of Türkiye, in 2020, 30,004 individuals were diagnosed with lung cancer, and 59% of these cases had distant metastasis at the time of diagnosis. These figures highlight that lung cancer is often diagnosed at an advanced stage, which significantly reduces survival rates (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2020). According to 2022 data from the World Health Organization (WHO) and GLOBOCAN, lung cancer ranks first among cancer-related deaths in Türkiye, accounting for one in every four cancer deaths.

According to the 2020 Türkiye Cancer Statistics published by the Public Health General Directorate; when examining the age-standardized rates of the 10 most common cancers by gender, trachea, bronchus, and lung cancers rank first among men with a rate of 51.9 per 100,000, while breast cancer ranks first among women with a rate of 43.4 per 100,000, followed by trachea, bronchus, and lung cancers with a rate of 10.2 per 100,000. Among all age groups, the most common cancer by gender is trachea, bronchus, and lung cancer in men (23.9%). In women, trachea, bronchus, and lung cancer ranks fourth (10.2%), following breast, thyroid, and colorectal cancers. When examining the age-specific incidence rates of the most common cancers in men, trachea, bronchus, and lung cancer is observed to be the one that peaks most rapidly in the 40–44 age group. When we examine the stage distribution of diagnosed cancer types in our country, we see that trachea, bronchus, and lung cancers are detected at the distant metastasis stage (stage 4) in 59% of cases (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı, 2020).

One of the most important reasons why lung cancer is diagnosed at an advanced stage is that the disease usually does not present with symptoms in its early stages. The lungs are organs with low pain perception, and patients often attribute symptoms such as coughing, sputum production, and shortness of breath to smoking, thus ignoring them. This results in delayed diagnosis and progression to advanced stages.

The impact of early diagnosis on survival is quite significant. In patients diagnosed at stage 1 or 2, the five-year survival rate can reach 60–80%, while in stage 4, this rate drops to 5–10%. Therefore, early diagnosis of lung cancer not only extends life expectancy but also improves quality of life and offers the opportunity for surgical intervention. Additionally, early diagnosis reduces the economic burden on the healthcare system and prevents workforce loss. At this point, the role of primary healthcare services and family physicians is of critical importance.

One of the most significant global developments in this area is the National Lung Screening Trial (NLST) published in the United States in 2011. In this study, more than 55,000 individuals aged 55–75 who were current or former smokers were evaluated. In the group screened with low-dose computed tomography (LDCT), a 20% reduction in lung cancer-related mortality was observed (National Lung Screening Trial Research Team, 2011). These results showed that LDCT is much more effective than chest radiography and led to the revision of screening guidelines.

However, like all screening programs, lung cancer screenings also have some disadvantages. False-positive results may lead to unnecessary further investigations or even risky surgical procedures. Additionally, repeated LDCT scans may expose healthy individuals to radiation, increasing their risk of developing cancer. Therefore, screening should only be recommended for individuals at high risk of developing the disease, who are eligible for surgery, and who do not have serious comorbidities that would limit their life expectancy (US Preventive Services Task Force, 2021).

European-based studies such as the NELSON trial have also shown that screening positively affects smoking cessation rates (van der Aalst et al., 2010). Countries like Canada and the United Kingdom also have screening programs with LDCT in place. Japan is one of the pioneering countries in this field. The ALCA project, which began in Tokyo in 1993, implemented LDCT screening as a pilot study. The results showed that more than 76% of individuals diagnosed in the early stage had a five-year survival rate (Japan Anti-Lung Cancer Association [ALCA], 1993).

Currently, there is no national lung cancer screening program in Türkiye. However, progress can be made in this area through stronger tobacco control efforts, the reinforcement of preventive healthcare services, and the accurate identification of high-risk individuals. Future screening programs must accurately identify high-risk groups, minimize potential harms, and be cost-effective to ensure successful implementation.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, early diagnosis in lung cancer saves lives. Family physicians play a crucial role in identifying and guiding high-risk individuals. Expanding scientifically-supported screening programs and raising awareness among healthcare professionals will be a significant gain for public health.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

GLOBOCAN. (2022). *Global Cancer Observatory*. International Agency for Research on Cancer.

<https://gco.iarc.fr/>

Japan Anti-Lung Cancer Association (ALCA). (1993). *LDCT screening program in Hitachi and Nagano Prefectures, Japan [Pilot study data summary]*.

National Lung Screening Trial Research Team. (2011). Reduced lung-cancer mortality with low-dose computed tomographic screening. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 365(5), 395–409.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1102873>

T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı Halk Sağlığı Genel Müdürlüğü. (2020). *Türkiye Kanseri İstatistikleri 2020*.

<https://hsgm.saglik.gov.tr/>

US Preventive Services Task Force. (2021). Screening for lung cancer: US Preventive Services Task Force recommendation statement. *JAMA*, 325(10), 962–970. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2021.1117>

van der Aalst, C. M., van den Bergh, K. A. M., Willemsen, M. C., de Koning, H. J., & van Klaveren, R. J. (2010). Lung cancer screening and smoking abstinence: 2-year follow-up data from the Dutch–Belgian randomised controlled lung cancer screening trial. *Thorax*, *65*(7), 600–605.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/thx.2009.133462>

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Selen Karaoglanoglu
Ordu University Faculty of Medicine
Department of Pulmonology
Ordu, Turkey
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9274-6237>
drselenu@gmail.com